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DYNAMICS OF THE CYTOKINE PROFILE OF THE ORAL FLUID IN PATIENTS WITH SETTON'S APHTHOSIS

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ABSTRACT

Diseases of the oral mucosa are one of the most complex, urgent problems of dentistry and so far, they are the least studied in terms of etiology, pathogenesis, diagnosis and especially treatment among other dental diseases. It is known that the development of aphthae is provoked by stimulation of COP keratinocytes by an unknown antigen, which, in turn, leads to the stimulation of T-lymphocytes and the release of cytokines and various interleukins. TNF- α is a major pro-inflammatory cytokine that has a chemotactic effect on neutrophils, stimulating the inflammatory cascade. Abnormalities in the cytokine mechanism (namely, increased levels of TNF- α , IL-2, IL-12 and decreased levels of IL-10) accelerate LPO, while reducing the ability of antioxidant defense mechanisms, which greatly increases oxidative stress. Due to the decrease in the concentration of IL-10, which acts to inhibit the release of cytokines, the inflammatory response is not suppressed, which leads to the development of the clinical picture of PAC. Modern ideas about the pathogenesis of AS note a significant role of cytokine profile imbalance in the occurrence and clinical manifestation of the pathology under study.

Keywords: cytokine profile, cytokine mechanism, T-lymphocytes, various interleukins, oral fluid, inflammatory response, TNF- α , IL-2, IL-12, IL-10.

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ДИНАМИКА ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ЦИТОКИНОВОГО ПРОФИЛЯ РОТОВОЙ ЖИДКОСТИ БОЛЬНЫХ С АФТОЗОМ СЕТТОНА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Заболевания слизистой оболочки полости рта являются одной из наиболее сложных, актуальных проблем стоматологии и до настоящего времени они наименее изучены с точки зрения этиологии, патогенеза, диагностики и особенно лечения среди других стоматологических заболеваний. Известно, что развитие афт провоцируется стимуляцией кератиноцитов COP неизвестным антигеном, что, в свою очередь, приводит к стимуляции Т-

лимфоцитов и высвобождению цитокинов и различных интерлейкинов. TNF- α - это основной провоспалительный цитокин, который оказывает хемотаксическое действие на нейтрофилы, стимулируя развитие каскада воспалительных реакций. Аномалии механизма цитокинов (а именно повышенный уровень TNF- α , IL-2, IL-12 и снижение уровня IL-10) ускоряют ПОЛ, при этом снижаются возможности антиоксидантных механизмов 21 защиты, что в значительной мере увеличивает окислительный стресс. Из-за снижения концентрации IL-10, который действует для ингибирования высвобождения цитокинов, воспалительная реакция не подавляется, что приводит к разворачиванию клинической картины РАС. Современные представления о патогенезе АС отмечают значительную роль дисбаланса цитокинового профиля в возникновении и клинической манифестации изучаемой патологии.

Ключивые слова: цитокиновый профиль, цитокиновый механизм, Т-лимфоциты, различные интерлейкины, ротовая жидкость, воспалительная реакция, TNF- α , IL-2, IL-12, IL-10.

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СЕТТОН АФТОЗИ БЎЛГАН БЕМОРЛАРДА ОҒИЗ БЎШЛИҒИ СУЮҚЛИГИНИ ЦИТОКИН ПРОФИЛИНИ ДИНАМИКАСИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Оғиз бўшлиғи шиллиқ қавати касалликлари стоматологиянинг энг мураккаб долзарб муаммоларидан бири бўлиб, бошқа тиш касалликлари орасида этиологияси, патогенези, диагностикаси ва айниқса даволаш нуқтаи назаридан энг кам ўрганилган. Маълумки, афталарнинг ривожланиши ОБШҚ (оғиз бўшлиғи шиллиқ қават) кератиноцитларини номаълум антиген томонидан кўзгатилиши билан кўзгатилади бу эса ўз навбатида Т-лимфоцитларнинг рағбатлантирилишига ва цитокинлар ва турли интерлейкинларнинг ажралиб чиқишига олиб келади. TNF- α асосий яллиғланишига қарши цитокин бўлиб, нейтрофилларга кемотактик таъсир кўрсатади, яллиғланиш каскадининг ривожланишини рағбатлантиради. Цитокин механизмидаги аномалиялар масалан, TNF- α , IL-2, IL-12 даражасининг ошиши ва IL-10 даражасининг пасайиши липидларни перекисли оксидланишини тезлаштиради, шу билан бирга антиоксидант химоя механизмларининг қобилиятини пасайтиради, бу эса стресс оксидланишни сезиларли даражада оширади. Цитокинларнинг чиқарилишини тўхтатилиши IL-10 консентратциясининг пасайиши туфайли яллиғланиш реакцияси босилмайди, бу ҚАС (қайталанувчи афтоз стоматит) клиник кўринишининг ривожланишига олиб келади. Сеттон афтоз патогенези ҳақидаги замонавий ғоялар ўрганилаётган патологиянинг пайдо бўлиши ва клиник кўринишида цитокин профилининг мувозанатининг муҳим ролини қайд этади.

Калит сўзлар: цитокин профили, цитокин механизми, Т-лифоцитлар, турли интерлейкинлар, оғиз суюқлиги, яллиғланиш реакцияси, TNF- α , IL-2, IL-12, IL-10.

Introduction. Diseases of the oral mucosa are one of the most complex, urgent problems of dentistry and so far they are the least studied in terms of etiology, pathogenesis, diagnosis and especially treatment among other dental diseases (1,2,11). The problem is further complicated by the fact that so far no specific measures for the prevention of diseases of the oral mucosa have been developed (2,3,5,12).

Of particular difficulty is the diagnosis and treatment of diseases of the oral mucosa with the development of erosive and ulcerative elements of the lesion, characterized by a recurrent and chronic course. These diseases include a severe form of recurrent aphthous stomatitis (Setton's aphtha). The development of this disease is accompanied by inflammation of the mucous membrane, severe pain

and duration of the course, polymorphism of clinical forms and low treatment efficiency, which is confirmed by the works of various authors (4,7,8,10,13). However, despite the variety of scientific studies conducted in our country and abroad, the etiopathogenesis of recurrent aphthous stomatitis remains the subject of numerous discussions. Since the formation of aphthous elements is accompanied by a pronounced pain reaction, leading to a violation of the quality of life of the patient (3,6,11).

It is known that the development of aphthae is provoked by stimulation of COP keratinocytes by an unknown antigen, which, in turn, leads to the stimulation of T-lymphocytes and the release of cytokines and various interleukins. TNF- α is a major pro-inflammatory cytokine that has a chemotactic effect on neutrophils, stimulating the inflammatory cascade. Abnormalities in the cytokine mechanism (namely, increased levels of TNF-a, IL-2, IL-12 and decreased levels of IL-10) accelerate LPO, while reducing the ability of antioxidant defense mechanisms, which greatly increases oxidative stress. Due to the decrease in the concentration of IL-10, which acts to inhibit the release of cytokines, the inflammatory response is not suppressed, which leads to the development of the clinical picture of PAC [10,11]. Modern ideas about the pathogenesis of AS note a significant role of cytokine profile imbalance in the occurrence and clinical manifestation of the pathology under study.

Purpose of the study. The dynamics of the cytokine profile of the oral fluid of patients with Setton's aphthosis.

Material and research methods.

Clinical studies were conducted on the basis of the Department of Hospital Therapeutic Dentistry of the TSDI for the period from 2020 to 2022. We examined 112 patients with severe chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis (Setton's aphthae) aged 25 to 60 years. The mean age of the patients was 46.7 ± 1.45 years.

To assess the indicators of local immunity of the oral cavity and the effectiveness of the treatment compared with the traditional method of treatment, we studied such indicators as the level of pro-inflammatory cytokines: interleukin-2 (IL-2), tumor necrosis factor-a (TNF- α), anti-inflammatory cytokine : interleukin-10 (IL-10).

For the study, unstimulated oral fluid was collected by spitting by the patient into a test tube on an empty stomach in a volume of 5 ml. The day before, the patient received recommendations on the specifics of preparing for the collection of culture fluid: in the morning do not eat, do not brush your teeth, do not use rinses, elixirs, do not smoke and do not use lipstick (both hygienic and cosmetic).

After taking the oral fluid, the tube was once tightly closed, it was assigned an individual number in accordance with the list of the study. All collected material immediately after sampling was frozen at a temperature of -18°C , stored in a freezer in a strictly vertical position, defrosted once and immediately before laboratory tests.

Quantitative determination of the content of TNF-a in the oral fluid was carried out by the method of solid-phase ELISA using mono- and polyclonal antibodies to TNF-a.

Quantitative determination of the content of IL-2 and IL-10 in the oral fluid was carried out by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) using mono- and polyclonal antibodies to human IL-2 and IL-10.

Next, the arithmetic mean values of the optical density were calculated for each pair of wells of the plate, which contained the calibration, control, and test samples. Based on the results obtained in linear coordinates, a calibration graph of the correlation of the arithmetic mean value of optical density from the concentration of IL-10 in the calibration samples (pg/ml) was built, and then the concentration of IL-10 in the control and analyzed samples was determined from the calibration graph.

Organization, systematization, primary processing of statistical data obtained during the dissertation research were carried out using Microsoft Office Excel (version 15.0) for a personal computer.

Results and its discussion.

It is known that disorders in the immune status in a number of diseases are based on defects in the system of cytokines, the main regulators of the processes of proliferation and differentiation of immunocompetent cells. It has been proven that many manifestations of chronic inflammatory diseases are associated with the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF- α , etc. In connection with these data, the study of the level of pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-4, TNF- α and IFN- γ allows you to obtain information about the functional activity of immunocompetent cells and the severity of the inflammatory process [Ketlinsky S.A., Kalinina N.M. Cytokines of mononuclear phagocytes in the regulation of inflammation and immunity // Immunology. - 1995. - No. 3. - S. 30-44.]

Modern ideas about the pathogenesis of AS note a significant role of cytokine profile imbalance in the occurrence and clinical manifestation of the pathology under study.

In our studies, it was found that during the dynamic assessment of the levels of individual cytokines, we revealed the following changes: an increase in the values of pro-inflammatory fractions - TNF- α , IL-2 and suppression of anti-inflammatory IL-10 in the oral fluid, which corresponded to the onset of clinical manifestations of AS as a typical inflammatory process (Table 1).

Table 1
Dynamics of the Cytokine Profile of the Oral Fluid of Patients with Setton's Aphthae

Indicators	Control group (healthy) n=15	Patients with Setton's aphthae (n=45)
TNF- α , pg/ml	6.42+0.68	8.69+0.66*
IL-2, pg/ml	11.54+2.39	18.65+1.62*
IL-10, pg/ml	8.69+0.49	2.35+0.36*
Lactoferrin, pg/ml	1.56 \pm 0.11	3.14 \pm 0.25*

Note: * - P<0.05 significance of differences when compared with the control group.

Prior to treatment, the average values of all studied cytokines in the oral fluid in CRAS patients were significantly higher than in healthy individuals (control group) (p<0.05). The levels of IL-2 and TNF- α in the oral fluid of CRAS patients exceeded the control values by 1.35 and -1.61 times.

Thus, the level of the pro-inflammatory cytokine TNF- α in the oral fluid of CRAS patients was higher and averaged 8.69+0.66 pg/ml, which was 1.35 times higher than the control values (6.42+0.68 pg/ml). ml) (p<0.001).

The level of IL-2 in the oral fluid of healthy people (control) averaged 11.54+2.39 pg/ml, while in the oral fluid of patients with Setton's aphthae, the average value of this mediator was 18.65+1.62 pg/ml, which was 1.61 times higher than in the control.

This circumstance indicates an increase in the intensity of the inflammatory process occurring in the cells of the oral mucosa. It should be noted that high values of IL-2 are controlled by the receptor antagonist and autoantibodies to it and indicate the depletion of the amount of the antagonist due to the chronic course of the disease.

At the same time, they limit the completeness of the cytokine's action, restraining the intensity of inflammation at the level of a chronic, but not acute, inflammatory process.

IL10 is known to have multiple pleiotropic effects on immunoregulation and inflammation. It reduces the expression of Th1 cytokines, MHC class II antigens, and co-stimulatory molecules on macrophages. Increases B-cell survival, proliferation and antibody production. In addition, it inhibits cytokine synthesis, antigen presentation, and CD4+ T cell activation and inhibits the induction of secretion of the inflammatory cytokines TNF IL-1 β , interleukin 12, and interferon-gamma mediated by lipopolysaccharide and other bacterial products.

When assessing the level of anti-inflammatory cytokine IL-10 in the oral fluid of the examined patients with CRAS, it was found that the level of IL-10 in the oral fluid averaged 2.35 ± 0.36 pg/ml, which was 3.54 times lower than the control values. (Control — 8.69 ± 0.49 pg/ml) ($p < 0.05$).

As you know, lactoferrin is a polyfunctional protein from the family of transferrins synthesized by epithelial cells and as one of the components of the immune system contained in various secretory fluids: saliva, nasal secretions, breast milk, blood neutrophils and mucosal epithelium. Lactoferrin is an important component of the system of non-specific antimicrobial protection of mucous membranes, has bacteriostatic properties due to the binding of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. In addition, lactoferrin reflects the degree of inflammatory reactions in the patient's body.

The analysis of the obtained research results indicates an increase in the level of lactoferrin in the oral fluid in AS patients by 2 times relative to the control group. An increase in the level of lactoferrin in the oral fluid reflects the intensity of neutrophil activation in biological fluids, being a systemic marker of the activity of the immune system of the oral mucosa. As mentioned above, lactoferrin belongs to the transferrin family of iron-binding and antibacterial proteins. In addition, lactoferrin interacts with glycosaminoglycans and proteoglycans of epithelial membranes, so areas with a high concentration of this protein may appear on the surface of mucosal cells. By binding iron, lactoferrin reduces its content in saliva, and hence its entry into the bacterial cell. This leads to a slowdown in the formation of heme-containing enzymes involved in the energy metabolism of bacteria. The lack of ATP inhibits the development and colonization of pathogenic microflora. Therefore, this protein is involved as an iron-capturing glycoprotein in various reactions of the body's defense against a microorganism and is involved in the regulation of the function of immunocompetent cells. In general, based on the results obtained, it can be stated that the marker of inflammation - lactoferrin - has a clinical diagnostic value in diseases of the oral mucosa.

Thus, in patients with AS, an increase in the concentration of pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-2 and TNF-alpha, as well as the concentration of lactoferrin in the oral fluid, was noted in the oral fluid. Based on the results obtained, it can be stated that the marker of inflammation - IL-12 and TNF-alpha and lactoferrin - has a clinical diagnostic value in diseases of the oral mucosa. In addition, the features of the cytokine profile of local immunity identified during the study in patients with Setton's aphthae play an important role in the choice of pathogenetic therapy, which must be taken into account when determining diagnostic and therapeutic tactics.

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